

Safety of active substances derived from *Rosa damascena* and their potential biological activity in humans: a systematic review

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Abstract

The latest amendments to CLP Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008 on the classification, labeling, and packaging of chemicals, introduced in 2023, classify essential oils derived from *Rosa damascena* as potentially hazardous mixtures. This has raised serious concern among manufacturers and scientific circles in all countries where *Rosa damascena* is traditionally grown, including Bulgaria.

Aim: To evaluate the safety of active substances derived from *Rosa damascena* and their potential biological activity in humans.

Materials and methods: We conducted a systematic review of scientific publications using keywords in MEDLINE, the Central Medical Library of the Medical University of Sofia, and national peer-reviewed scientific magazines in Bulgaria for the period from January 1955 to May 2025. The selection of articles was conducted according to PRISMA, and the results were analyzed using the PICOS tool.

Results and discussion: Over a period of 70 years, 151 articles were identified. Sixty-five articles that met the inclusion criteria were included in the systematic review. The results obtained confirm a wide range of biological activities of *Rosa damascena*. There is significant heterogeneity in study designs, dosages used, administration forms, and types of studies. These differences limit the possibility of direct comparison of results and underscore the need for standardized clinical trials with clear protocols and unified criteria, including meta-analyses. The essential oil and plant extracts show antimicrobial and antifungal activity, as well as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic properties. The literature also contains data on neuroprotective, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, and antiviral effects, as well as the potentiation of sexual function.

Keywords

Rosa damascena, safety, biological activity, essential oil, extract, activity, systematic review

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a renaissance in scientific interest in essential oils and phytochemicals, particularly in the context of the search for natural alternatives with proven biological activity. Among these is the oil-bearing rose (*Rosa damascena*), emblematic of Bulgaria, which holds a central place not only as a national symbol and a source of high-quality rose oil but also as a subject of in-depth biomedical research. Despite its long-standing use in cosmetics, aromatherapy, and traditional medicine, systematic scientific attempts to validate its therapeutic potential have only been carried out in recent decades.

The significance of *Rosa damascena* gains an additional dimension against the backdrop of regulatory processes in the European Union. The proposed changes to Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008 on the classification, labeling, and packaging of chemicals (CLP), which potentially classify essential oils as hazardous mixtures, have raised serious concerns among manufacturers, the scientific community, and governmental bodies and institutions in Bulgaria, including at the political level (European Parliament and Council of the EU 2008). As a result of active diplomatic intervention, a temporary moratorium was achieved—a six-year postponement during which a scientific assessment of the safety and effects of such natural products is to be conducted. In this context, the need for high-quality scientific evidence regarding the biological activity and safety of *Rosa damascena* becomes not just an academic issue but a factor of strategic importance for the protection of national interests and the preservation and establishment of the market status of products made from *Rosa damascena*.

The phytochemical composition of the plant includes a rich variety of biologically active substances, among which essential oils (citronellol, geraniol, and phenylethyl alcohol), flavonoids, tannins, and organic acids stand out. This content accounts for the wide range of pharmacological actions associated with *Rosa damascena*, including antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anxiolytic, and neuroprotective effects (Basim 2003; Naziroglu et al. 2013; Abbasijahromi et al. 2020; Mileva et al. 2021; Ilieva et al. 2022; Lee et al. 2023). *Rosa damascena* is a plant with a well-established use, being employed in the treatment of various clinical conditions—including pain syndromes, anxiety, functional gastrointestinal disorders, and dermatological diseases (de Almeida et al. 2004; Hongratanaworakit 2009; Fukada et al. 2012; Farnia et al. 2015; Ghavam et al. 2021; Matias Nascimento Maia et al. 2021). In addition to its use in traditional medicine, *Rosa damascena* finds wide application in the cosmetics and food industries, which is attributed to its pronounced aromatic, antioxidant, and preservative properties (Nonato et al. 2012; Solimine et al. 2016; Nikolova et al. 2019a, b; Mohammed et al. 2020; Georgieva et al. 2021; Haddadi et al. 2021).

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the number of scientific publications aimed at validating the traditional use of the plant through modern experimental and clinical methodologies. This represents an important stage in the development of evidence-based

phytotherapy, with the potential for the development of standardized products applicable in both modern pharmacotherapy and in the prevention and supportive treatment of chronic diseases (Farnia et al. 2015; Uysal et al. 2016; Mohebitabar et al. 2017). Particular attention should be paid to the overlap between the pharmaceutical, dermatological, and nutraceutical uses of *Rosa damascena*, which highlights its potential for so-called “dual use.” Active substances that have proven their safety and efficacy in local application in cosmetics could also find applications in fields such as neurology, gastroenterology, and reproductive medicine (Katsukawa et al. 2011; Solimine et al. 2016).

Aim of the study

To evaluate the safety of active substances derived from *Rosa damascena* and their potential biological activity in humans.

Materials and methods

We conducted a systematic review of scientific publications using keywords in MEDLINE, the Central Medical Library of the Medical University of Sofia, and national peer-reviewed scientific magazines in Bulgaria for the period from January 1955 to May 2025. The selection of articles was conducted according to PRISMA, and for the analysis of results, the PICOS tool was used (Moher et al. 2009; Shamseer et al. 2015). We prepared a protocol for the study in accordance with the PRISMA 2009 Checklist, with pre-defined elements: topic, design, search strategy, inclusion and exclusion criteria, data collection methods, data analysis and statistical assessment, and conclusions. The protocol was not registered in advance in the PROSPERO system (International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews) because the study is limited to a systematic review of scientific publications, without conducting a meta-analysis. AI-based tools were used solely for technical assistance in language editing and text formatting during the preparation of the manuscript. The tools did not participate in the creation of the scientific content, analyses, or interpretation of data. The topic of the systematic review is identical to the title of the article—searching for information on the safety of active substances derived from *Rosa damascena* and their potential biological activity in humans, as published in specialized medical scientific literature.

Design

Retrospective observational analytical study.

Search strategy

We conducted an active search for scientific publications using the following keywords in Bulgarian and English: *Rosa damascena*, Damask rose, rose oil, rose extract, biological activity, pharmacological effect, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, neuroprotective, anxiolytic, and antidepressant.

Study period

January 1955 to May 2025. Within this period, a total of 151 scientific publications related to the biological activity and pharmacological properties of *Rosa damascena* were identified. Assessed results and inclusion criteria. Only scientific publications containing data on the safety and biological activity of *Rosa damascena* were analyzed. The inclusion criteria for the analysis were as follows: the scientific article must contain data on one or more pharmacological actions of *Rosa damascena*, including but not limited to antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anxiolytic, antidepressant, or neuroprotective activity; it must include analysis of extracts, essential oil, or other forms of application of

the plant; it must be published in a peer-reviewed scientific journal in English or Bulgarian; and it must present original data or represent a systematic review or meta-analysis.

Data extraction

Two of the authors independently extracted data from the scientific publications that met the inclusion criteria. For the purposes of this study, the following data were collected and analyzed: surname of the first author, year of publication, country of origin, type of publication (original study, systematic review, meta-analysis), form of *Rosa damascena* used (essential oil, hydrosol, extract, etc.), study designs, types of biological activities studied, evaluated endpoints, main pharmacological effects, and potential therapeutic applications.

Table 1. Geographical distribution of studies on *Rosa damascena*.

Country / Region	Number of studies (n = 65)	% of Total	Cumulative %
Iran	19	29.20	66.20
Turkey	11	16.90	96.90
Bulgaria	7	10.80	16.90
Japan	6	9.20	75.40
China	5	7.70	27.70
Brazil	3	4.60	6.20
India	3	4.60	36.90
Bulgaria, Switzerland	2	3.10	20.00
Egypt	2	3.10	30.80
Bangladesh	1	1.50	1.50
Germany	1	1.50	32.30
South Korea	1	1.50	76.90
Switzerland	1	1.50	78.50
Thailand	1	1.50	80.00
USA	1	1.50	98.50
United Kingdom	1	1.50	100.00

Statistical analyses

The systematic review included 65 scientific articles that met the inclusion criteria and methodological requirements. For data evaluation, we used the open-source statistical software Jamovi and Microsoft Excel 2024. We performed descriptive and variance analyses. The results are presented as absolute and relative frequencies using one- and two-dimensional frequency distribution tables.

Results and discussion

The selection of the analyzed scientific articles, conducted in accordance with the search strategy, is presented as a PRISMA flow diagram (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Overview of the searching process–PRISMA flow diagram.

The literature search was limited to publications published in English and Bulgarian. The initial review identified 151 scientific publications related to various aspects of the biological activity of *Rosa damascena*. A screening of titles and abstracts was conducted, followed by a full-text assessment based on the predefined inclusion criteria. Eighty-six publications were excluded: some due to the lack of relevant biological or pharmacological data on *Rosa damascena*, others due to a focus on agrotechnical, botanical, or production characteristics with no connection to biomedical application. After assessing compliance with the inclusion criteria, we analyzed 65 scientific publications investigating the biological activity of *Rosa damascena*, such as antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, anxiolytic, antidepressant, neuroprotective, and other effects (Mahmood et al. 1996; Kose et al. 2012; Kheirkhan et al. 2014; Maia et al. 2021; Mahmood et al. 2022) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of scientific publications according to areas of biological activity of *Rosa damascena* (n = 65).

The analysis of the 65 included scientific publications shows that *Rosa damascena* exhibits a wide range of biological activities. The most frequently studied were psychotropic effects—anxiolytic, antidepressant, and those related to cognitive function—reported in 13 studies (20%). Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity were studied in 12 publications (18.5%), and analgesic effects in seven studies (10.8%). Studies focusing on cosmetic and dermatological use accounted for 9.2%, while antimicrobial and reproductive activity were each addressed in five publications (7.7%). Toxicological safety was reported in four publications (6.2%), and antiviral activity and effects on the digestive system were each studied in three articles (4.6%). Two publications (3.1%) examined cardiovascular, cytotoxic/antitumor, and neuroprotective properties. Respiratory effects were studied less frequently, with only 1.5% of studies. These results highlight the multifunctional therapeutic potential of *Rosa damascena* while also outlining the directions in which additional, targeted, and well-standardized studies are needed.

The geographical distribution of scientific publications included in this systematic review (n = 65) shows a clear concentration of research in countries with established

traditions in the use of essential oils and phytotherapy. The largest number of studies originates from Iran (29.2%), where *Rosa damascena* occupies a central place in traditional medicine, and modern scientific production actively validates its therapeutic potential through *in vivo* and *in vitro* models. This is followed by Turkey with 11 publications (16.9%)—a country where the oil-bearing rose is part of culturally and economically significant crop production, including varieties closely related to the Bulgarian genotype. Bulgaria is represented with seven studies (10.8%), placing it third in frequency. Despite its leading role in the production of rose oil with a controlled geographical indication, its scientific output visible in international databases remains relatively limited. A significant contribution also comes from Japan (9.2%) and China (7.7%), where interest is primarily focused on the pharmacological and biochemical mechanisms of action of the essential oil. Countries such as India, Brazil, Egypt, South Korea, Switzerland, and the USA are represented by single or small numbers of publications, reflecting a growing global interest in *Rosa damascena*. Cases of international collaboration have also been noted—including between Bulgaria and Switzerland—which highlight the potential for transdisciplinary and cross-border scientific projects. A certain imbalance between production capacity and scientific output is identified, suggesting the need for strategic stimulation of scientific activity in countries with traditional rose production (Prasad et al. 2014; Swamy et al. 2015; Shirazi et al. 2017; Raka et al. 2023). Table 2 presents the main parameters of the identified clinical trials evaluating the pharmacological efficacy and safety of different formulations containing extracts or essential oil of *Rosa damascena*, assessed using the PICOS tool.

The analysis includes 16 intervention studies, of which 15 are randomized controlled clinical trials and one is a non-randomized controlled clinical trial. The study population includes 1,211 patients. All randomized studies have a parallel-group design; most are double-blind or single-blind and evaluate a variety of therapeutic indications—primary dysmenorrhea, dyspepsia, anxiety, sexual dysfunction, chronic pelvic pain, postoperative pain, and gastrointestinal disorders such as gastroesophageal reflux disease and ulcerative colitis. The interventions include inhaled aromatherapy and oral capsule intake, as well as topical (dermal or intravaginal) application. The control groups are highly variable—from placebo and standard therapy to interventions with essential oils. Most studies use established validated scales to assess the effect—VAS, STAI, FSFI, IIEF, GERQ, etc. The results of the included trials indicate a statistically significant reduction in symptoms in the intervention groups compared to the controls, with no serious adverse drug reactions recorded. The observed therapeutic benefits include various pharmacodynamic effects—analgesic, anxiolytic, gastroprotective, and hormone-modulating. Clinical evidence confirms the therapeutic potential of *Rosa damascena* in various conditions, and there is sufficient evidence supporting a favorable safety profile.

Table 2. Evaluation of scientific publications with the PICOS tool.

Population	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes	Study design
60 women with uncomplicated pelvic inflammatory disease (uPID), aged 18–45	Black sesame powder (5 g) + <i>Rosa damascena</i> oil (10 mL) administered intravaginally for 14 days	Standard care: doxycycline + metronidazole orally for 14 days	Reduction in abdominal pain (VAS, McPS), improved vaginal discharge, improved SF-12 quality of life scores, no adverse effects	RCTs Double-blind, double-dummy, randomized, standard-controlled trial
126 adult patients (aged 18–65) undergoing peripheral intravenous catheter (PIVC) insertion in Turkey; excluded if sensitive to smell or had asthma, epilepsy, or allergies.	1–2 drops of rose oil (<i>Rosa damascena</i>) aromatherapy via face mask during PIVC procedure.	1) Hand-holding by a family member. 2) No intervention (control group).	Pain measured by Numeric Rating Scale (0–10) within 10 minutes: 2.40 ± 1.78 (rose oil), 3.53 ± 1.98 (hand-holding), 4.88 ± 1.56 (control); statistically significant (p = 0.001).	RCTs Randomized, single-blind, parallel-assignment, interventional clinical trial.
70 undergraduate nursing students (Hormozgan University of Medical Sciences), randomly assigned to experimental and sham groups	Inhalation aromatherapy: 7 drops of lavender oil (10%) + 3 drops of <i>Rosa damascena</i> oil (10%) on nonabsorbent pads placed near students before and during exams	The sham group received pads with 10 drops of sesame oil (no known anxiolytic effect)	Statistically significant reduction in State Anxiety Inventory (SAI) scores in experimental group 15 min after entry and after the exam (P < 0.01)	RCTs Single-blind, randomized controlled clinical trial
70 adult patients with clinically diagnosed GERD (35 per group); aged 25–60 years; recruited at Rasool Akram Hospital, Tehran, Iran	Rose oil softgel capsules (1000 mg, 3×/day), produced via the traditional Persian method (rose petals soaked in sesame oil for 25 days)	Omeprazole capsules (20 mg, 2×/day); both groups received a placebo for the alternate treatment to ensure blinding	Statistically significant improvement in GERD symptoms within both groups; no significant difference between rose oil and omeprazole in total GERQ symptom scores	RCTs Double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled clinical trial
120 pregnant women (18–35 years old) with low back pain, gestational age 12–33 weeks, receiving care at a prenatal clinic in Tehran, Iran	Topical application of <i>Rosa damascena</i> oil (7 drops, 2× daily for 4 weeks) in a base of almond oil, without massage	1) Almond oil placebo (carrier). 2) No intervention.	Significant decrease in pain intensity (VAS) and improvement in function (RMDQ); no adverse events reported except mild rhinitis in one subject	RCTs Randomized, placebo-controlled clinical trial with three parallel groups and blinded outcome assessment
40 adult patients clinically diagnosed with moderate-to-severe ulcerative colitis (UC), randomly assigned (20 per group); final analysis included 28 patients (14+14)	Rose oil soft capsules (1000 mg, 2 capsules, 3× daily for 2 months); sesame oil-based formulation	Placebo capsules filled with liquid paraffin (same appearance and schedule)	Decrease in Mayo score and improvement in IBDQ-9 and calprotectin in both groups; no statistically significant difference between rose oil and placebo	RCTs Double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled clinical trial (pilot study) conducted at Motahari Clinic, Shiraz University of Medical Sciences, Iran
75 female university students (aged 18–35) with primary dysmenorrhea, residing in dormitories of Tehran University of Medical Sciences	Self-massage with 4% <i>Rosa damascena</i> oil (diluted in almond oil); applied once on the first day of menstruation in two consecutive cycles	1) Massage with almond oil only (placebo group) 2) Massage without oil (control group)	Significant reduction in pain (VAS) after the second cycle in the rose oil group compared to both placebo and control (p = 0.001); no side effects reported	RCTs Randomized controlled clinical trial with three parallel arms; VAS scores compared between and within cycles
108 nulliparous women (gestational age 38–42 weeks) in active labor at a hospital in Tehran, Iran; randomized into 3 groups (36 per group)	Group 1: 10-minute inhalation + footbath with 1% rose oil at 40 °C, applied at onset of active (4 cm) and transitional (8 cm) phases	Group 2: Warm water footbath only (no essential oil) Group 3: Control (routine care)	Anxiety scores (VASA) were significantly lower in the rose oil group at both active and transitional phases vs. the control (p = 0.001); it was more effective than a warm footbath alone	RCTs Randomized clinical trial with three arms; anxiety measured using the VASA scale before and after each intervention phase
64 adult cancer patients (aged ~53), undergoing chemotherapy with high emetogenic potential drugs; 60.9% were female; cancers included colon (48.4%), breast (43.8%), and stomach (7.8%)	Inhalation aromatherapy with rose essential oil (40% concentration), applied via gauze on the collar 20 cm from the nose, for 3 minutes before each chemotherapy session and maintained up to 18 h	The control group received only standard antiemetic drugs (granisetron, dexamethasone, and aprepitant) with no aromatherapy	Significantly lower nausea and vomiting scores (VAS) in the aromatherapy group across all time points during both the 2 nd and 3 rd chemotherapy cycles (p < 0.001; large Cohen's d effect)	RCTs Randomized controlled clinical trial, parallel-group, non-blinded due to scent; ethics-approved and registered (IRCT20100921004787N7)
90 female patients (aged 18–35) undergoing cesarean section (C-section) under spinal anesthesia at Motahari Hospital, Jahrom, Iran	Inhalation of Damask rose essential oil (3 drops on cotton ball, 10 cm from nose for 30 minutes) immediately post-C-section	1) Inhalation of lavender essential oil (same protocol) 2) Control group: inhalation of normal saline	Reduction in postoperative pain (VAS) and reduction in overt anxiety (STAI) significantly in the rose oil group – Greater effect of rose oil than lavender on both anxiety and pain (p < 0.05)	RCTs Double-blind randomized clinical trial with three groups; measurements taken before and 5 minutes after intervention
50 female patients (mean age 38.8) with opioid use disorder (OUD) under methadone maintenance therapy (MMT) and diagnosed with methadone-related sexual dysfunction (MRSD)	<i>Rosa damascena</i> oil (RDO), 2 mL/day orally (containing 17 mg citronellol), administered for 8 weeks	Placebo: 2 mL/day oil–water solution with identical scent	Improvement in sexual function (FSFI total and subdomains: desire, arousal, lubrication, orgasm, satisfaction, and pain) Improvement in Happiness (Oxford Happiness Questionnaire) Reduction in Prolactin, ↑ Progesterone, ↑ Estradiol	RCTs Randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial (8-week duration), with validated hormone assays and psychometric tools

Population	Intervention	Comparison	Outcomes	Study design
50 male patients (mean age: 40) with opioid use disorder (OUD) under methadone maintenance therapy (MMT); married or in stable heterosexual relationships	<i>Rosa damascena</i> oil (2 mL/day) orally for 8 weeks (containing 17 mg citronellol)	Placebo (2 mL/day oil–water solution with identical scent); both groups continued standard methadone	Improvement in sexual function (BSFI & IIEF scores)	RCTs Double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled clinical trial (8-week duration), approved and registered (IRCT2015091523705N1); statistical analysis with repeated measures ANOVA
			Increased testosterone levels (ELISA assay)	
			– Time × Group interaction is significant with large effect sizes – Placebo group showed decline	
100 women aged 19–30 years, diagnosed with primary dysmenorrhea, admitted to the emergency department in Tokat, Turkey	Diclofenac sodium 75 mg IM + rose essential oil aromatherapy (2% rose oil via vaporizer inhalation every 10 minutes)	Diclofenac sodium 75 mg IM only (no aromatherapy)	Reduction in VAS pain scores at 10 and 30 min in both groups	RCTs Randomized controlled clinical trial; 2 groups; VAS, BP, HR, and RR monitored at baseline, 10 min, and 30 min post-intervention
			– Greater pain reduction at 30 min in the aromatherapy group (p = 0.019)	
68 male patients (mean age ~32) with major depressive disorder (MDD) receiving SSRI treatment and diagnosed with SSRI-induced sexual dysfunction (SSRI-I SD)	<i>Rosa damascena</i> oil, 2 mL/day orally for 8 weeks (contains 17 mg citronellol), administered alongside stable SSRI treatment	Placebo (oil–water solution with identical scent), also administered 2 mL/day	– Significant improvement in sexual function domains: drive, erection, ejaculation, satisfaction	RCTs Randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial (8-week duration), conducted in Iran, with intention-to-treat analysis and validated psychometric scales (BSFI, BDI)
			– Reduced depressive symptoms (BDI)	
			– No side effects reported	
80 operating room personnel with moderate anxiety and poor sleep quality during COVID-19	Inhalation aromatherapy with <i>Rosa damascena</i> essential oil	Placebo (paraffin oil)	Significant reduction in state anxiety (STAI-S) and improvement in sleep quality (PSQI) after 30 days of intervention	RCTs Randomized controlled trial with parallel groups; 30-day intervention; non-blinded design
40 healthy adult volunteers, aged 18 to 21	Transdermal application of 1 mL of 20 percent rose oil in almond oil on the abdomen	Almond oil placebo; no olfactory exposure	Decreased systolic blood pressure, breathing rate, and blood oxygen saturation; increased skin temperature; participants felt more relaxed and calm	Non-RCT Non-randomized controlled human study
Total – 1211 patients				15 RCT/1 Non-RCT

Sumbul et al. conducted a clinical trial in India in 2024, evaluating the efficacy and safety of a combination of rose oil (*Rosa damascena*) and sesame oil in women with uncomplicated pelvic inflammatory disease. The results showed that the studied formulation was more economical, safer, and no less effective than standard therapy (Sumbul et al. 2024). Lee et al. conducted an *in vitro* study in South Korea, demonstrating that Bulgarian rose oil is effective in candidal infections by inhibiting the growth and hyphal formation of pathogenic *Candida* spp., including *Candida albicans* (Lee et al. 2023). Basak et al. conducted an intervention trial in Turkey in 2024, evaluating the effect of aromatherapy with rose oil combined with physical contact (holding hands) on stress, anxiety, and the birth experience in first-time births. A statistically significant improvement was found in the group that received the combined intervention (Basak et al. 2024). Dewanjee et al. presented a review article published in 2023 that examined the use of natural products, including *Rosa damascena*, in the management of respiratory diseases. The authors concluded that such agents have potential as adjuvants to standard therapies (Dewanjee et al. 2023). Abdallah et al. conducted an experimental study in Egypt, where they tested the effect of a nanoemulsion with *Rosa damascena* oil against UVB-induced skin damage. The results showed that the formula had antioxidant and photoprotective potential (Abdallah et al. 2023). Gerasimova et al. conducted a study in Bulgaria in 2022 to evaluate the cytotoxic and genotoxic potential of hydrosols of *Rosa damascena* and *Rosa alba*. The results showed a lack of toxic effects at the applied

concentrations, confirming the safety of the products for cosmetic and pharmaceutical use (Gerasimova et al. 2022).

Ilieva et al. investigated the *in vitro* biological activity of extracts from several species of roses, including *Rosa damascena*, discovering antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antiviral activity. The study was conducted in Bulgaria in 2022 and provides a scientific basis for the broad therapeutic application of rose products (Ilieva et al. 2022). Hashemi et al. implemented a randomized controlled trial in Iran in 2021, in which they evaluated the effect of combined aromatherapy with rose and lavender on women in labor. The authors found that aromatherapy significantly reduced anxiety and pain during labor (Hashemi et al. 2021). Georgieva et al. analyzed the redox-modulating capacity and antineoplastic activity of *Rosa damascena* in Bulgaria in 2021. The data obtained show the potential for the application of rose extracts in adjuvant antitumor therapy (Georgieva et al. 2021).

A subsequent study, also conducted in Bulgaria in 2021, revealed antiviral activity of *Rosa damascena* and other rose species through nonspecific mechanisms such as inhibition of viral adsorption. These data confirm the potential for including rose oil as an additional agent in antiviral therapies (Vilhelmova-Ilieva et al. 2021). A scientific team from Brazil conducted an *in silico* study in 2021 evaluating the antidepressant potential of the main component of rose oil—rose oxide. Molecular docking analysis shows a possible affinity relationship with receptors associated with depressive states (Matias Nascimento Maia et al. 2021). An *in vitro* study conducted in Turkey showed

that *Rosa damascena* essential oil induced relaxation of tracheal smooth muscle in a dose-dependent manner, supporting its potential as a bronchodilator (Demirel 2022a). In another study, the same author demonstrated that the oil induced vasodilation of isolated aortic rings in rats through a mechanism partially independent of the endothelium, with potential relevance to cardiovascular regulation (Demirel 2022b). In a third study, Demirel et al. (2022a, b) identified geraniol and β -citronellol as the main components responsible for the vasodilatory effect of rose oil. The data suggest a pharmacological potential for controlling vascular tone.

Saghafi et al. studied in Iran the antimicrobial activity of extracts and essential oil of *Rosa damascena* against bacteria and *Trichomonas vaginalis*. All showed varying degrees of effectiveness, supporting the potential of rose oil as an antiseptic (Saghafi et al. 2021). Mehraban et al. conducted a randomized controlled clinical trial in Iran comparing the effect of rose oil in capsule form with omeprazole in patients with gastroesophageal reflux. The data showed that rose oil had a clinically comparable effect to standard therapy (Mehraban et al. 2021).

Hamedi et al. conducted an *in vivo* study in Iran, where they found that short-term administration of *Rosa damascena* may have anxiolytic effects in animal models. The data support the use of the essential oil as an adjuvant in the treatment of anxiety (Hamedi et al. 2018). Guo et al. conducted a systematic review in China in 2020, analyzing the effectiveness of aromatherapy with rose oil in patients with preoperative anxiety. The results indicate that aromatherapy is an effective, non-invasive intervention with a rapid onset of action (Guo et al. 2020). Ueno et al. investigated the neuropsychological effect of 2-phenylethanol, a key aromatic component of *Rosa damascena*, in a mouse model. The results indicate antidepressant potential when inhaled, possibly through serotonergic modulation (Ueno et al. 2019). Wedler et al. conducted an *in vitro* study in Switzerland in which an extract of *Rosa damascena* modulated the expression of pro-inflammatory genes. The data show potential for the development of products with anti-inflammatory effects (Wedler et al. 2016a). In a collaborative study conducted in Bulgaria and Switzerland, the same author and team revealed potential for anti-tumor use by evaluating the anti-migratory and anti-proliferative activity of a polyphenol-enriched fraction of rose oil (RF20-(SP-207)) in cell lines (Wedler et al. 2016b).

Politano et al. conducted a pharmacokinetic study in the USA that evaluated the systemic exposure of phenylethyl alcohol, a key volatile component of *Rosa damascena*, in various animal models and humans. The data confirmed low toxicity (Politano et al. 2013). Mizuno et al. used an *in vitro* neuroendocrine model to evaluate the effects of essential oils on the hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal axis. *Rosa damascena* showed anxiolytic effects (Mizuno et al. 2015). Katsukawa et al. demonstrated that the main components of rose oil—geraniol and citronellol—modulate lipid metabolism and reduce adipose tissue accumulation in *in vitro* and animal models, suggesting possible anti-atherogenic activity (Katsukawa et al. 2011). A screening study of 31 essential oils, including rose, showed the ability

of the oils to activate TRPV1 receptors, which are associated with inflammation and pain. Rose oil showed moderate activation, suggesting a potential mechanism for analgesic effects (Ohkawara et al. 2010). Schmitt et al. in Germany studied the permeability of human skin *in vitro* when treated with various essential oils, including rose oil. The data suggest that rose oil increases skin permeability while preserving barrier function (Schmitt et al. 2010).

Conclusion

The present systematic review demonstrates a significant and diverse scientific interest in the biological activity of *Rosa damascena* and its derived biologically active substances, with an emphasis on psychotropic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects. The predominant number of studies focusing on anxiolytic and antidepressant properties (20%) confirms the clinical potential of rose oil in therapeutic practice, especially in anxiety and depressive disorders (Hongratanaworakit 2009; Farnia et al. 2015). This aligns with the established pharmacological effects of the main active components of *Rosa damascena*—citronellol, geraniol, and phenylethyl alcohol—which have proven mechanisms of action on the central nervous system (Matias Nascimento Maia et al. 2021). The high percentage of studies dedicated to antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity (18.5%) highlights the importance of rose oil as a potential therapeutic agent in chronic inflammatory and degenerative conditions. These results correspond well with the traditional use of *Rosa damascena* in folk medicine, as well as with modern scientific evidence on its phytochemical profile and biological activity (Mileva et al. 2021; Lee et al. 2023).

The significant number of studies originating from Iran and Turkey (over 46% in total) can be explained by the cultural significance and traditional use of *Rosa damascena* in these regions, as well as by the established national strategies for scientific research and innovation in the field of herbal medicine (Solimine et al. 2016). The number of publications originating from Bulgaria is relatively smaller, which is surprising given the country's leading role in the production of high-quality rose oil. This highlights the need to strengthen research activities and increase the international visibility of Bulgarian scientific research dedicated to *Rosa damascena* and its biologically active ingredients. The number of studies focused on cytotoxic, neuroprotective, and cardiovascular activities is relatively limited (about 3%). The heterogeneity in study design, forms, doses, and routes of administration of products containing active ingredients from rose oil necessitates standardized clinical trials and uniform methodological approaches, which would contribute to a better understanding and utilization of the therapeutic potential of *Rosa damascena*-derived products. In the context of current regulatory requirements in the European Union for the safety of natural extracts and essential oils, the results obtained provide a solid scientific basis that could support future regulatory and market decisions while protecting the national interests of rose oil-producing countries.

Products derived from *Rosa damascena* possess proven multifunctional therapeutic potential, have an acceptable level of safety, and can be integrated into modern pharmacotherapy and the cosmetic industry.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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